

TIME AND TEMPERATURE DEPENDENCE OF STATIC, CREEP, AND FATIGUE BEHAVIOR FOR FRP ADHESIVE JOINTS

Yasushi Miyano¹, Masayuki Nakada¹, Toshiaki Yonemori¹, Sangwook Sihn²,
and Stephen W. Tsai²

¹ *Materials System Research Laboratory, Kanazawa Institute of Technology,
Yatsukaho, Matto, Ishikawa 924-0838, Japan*

² *Department of Aeronautics & Astronautics, Stanford University,
Stanford, California 94305-4035, U.S.A.*

SUMMARY: We proposed a prediction method of fatigue life for polymer composite structures under an arbitrary frequency, stress ratio (minimum stress/maximum stress), and temperature from the results of constant strain-rate (CSR) test under various temperatures and loading rates, and fatigue tests at a single frequency under various temperatures. Tensile tests of GFRP/metal adhesive joints for CSR and fatigue loadings were conducted for various temperatures and loading rates. The validity of this method was proven for the tensile fatigue life for the GFRP/metal adhesive joints from these test results. Furthermore, the characteristic time-temperature dependent fatigue behavior of this FRP joints was clarified using this prediction method.

KEYWORDS: GFRP, Joints, Fatigue strength, Life prediction, Time-dependent properties

INTRODUCTION

It is well known that the mechanical behavior of polymer resins exhibits time and temperature dependence, called viscoelastic behavior, not only above the glass transition temperature T_g but also below T_g . Thus, it can be presumed that the mechanical behavior of polymer composites also significantly depends on time and temperature. It has been confirmed that the viscoelastic behavior of polymer resins as matrices is a major influence on the time and temperature dependence of the mechanical behavior of FRP [1-7].

In previous papers, we proposed a prediction method for the fatigue life of polymer composites under an arbitrary frequency, stress ratio, and temperature from the data measured by constant strain-rate tests at several strain-rates and various temperatures, and fatigue tests at a single frequency and various temperatures. The validity of this method and the hypotheses was confirmed by three-point bending tests of strain-woven CFRP laminates and others [10,11]. The validity was also proven for the tensile behavior of GFRP/metal adhesive joints in which a brittle epoxy resin is used for adhesives [9].

In this paper, the validity of the prediction method is discussed for the case of the tensile

behavior of GFRP/metal adhesive joint in which a ductile PMMA resin is used for adhesives. Furthermore the time and temperature dependence of fatigue behavior for this FRP joint is characterized by using these results.

PREDICTION PROCEDURE

- T, T_0 : temperature, reference temperature
- f, f' : frequency, reduced frequency
- t_s, t_c, t_f : time to failure under constant elongation rate (CER), creep and fatigue loading
- t_s', t_c', t_f' : reduced time to failure
- $a_{T_0}(T)$: time-temperature shift factor
($a_{T_0}(T) = t_s/t_s' = t_c/t_c' = t_f/t_f' = f'/f$)
- R : load ratio ($R = P_{min}/P_{max}$)
- N_f : number of cycles to failure ($N_f = f t_f$)
- P_s, P_c, P_f : CER, creep, and fatigue failure load
- $P_{f:0}, P_{f:1}$: P_f for $R = 0$ and $R = 1$

Fig.1: Prediction procedure of fatigue life for polymer composites and structures.

A prediction method for fatigue failure load of composite structures under an arbitrary frequency, load ratio (minimum load/maximum load), and temperature rests on the four hypotheses, (A) same failure mechanism for constant elongation-rate (CER), creep, and fatigue failure, (B) same time-temperature superposition principle for all failure loads, (C) linear cumulative damage law for monotonic loading, and (D) linear dependence of fatigue failure load upon load ratio. When these hypotheses are met, the fatigue failure load for an arbitrary combination of frequency, load ratio, and temperature can be determined based on the master curves of CER failure load and fatigue failure load for zero load ratio. The master curve of CER failure load can be constructed from the test results at several elongation-rates for various temperatures. On the other hand, the master curve of fatigue failure load for zero load ratio can be constructed from the test results at a single frequency for various temperatures using the time-temperature superposition principle for the CER failure load. The outline of this method is shown schematically in Fig.1 together with definitions of some notations.

EXPERIMENTAL PROCEDURE

Preparation of GFRP/Metal Adhesive Joints

The GFRP/metal adhesive joints (FRP joint) was made from a GFRP pipe, ductile cast iron rod, and adhesive resin as shown in Fig.2. The adhesive resin is PMMA resin, PLEXUS^{AE} AO425 (ITW Adhesives). Ductile cast iron rod is made from ductile iron castings Grade 80-55-06 (ASTM A 536-84). The adhesive resin thickness and length of FRP joint are respectively 4mm and 28mm.

Test Procedure

The tensile tests for CER and fatigue loadings were conducted for various temperatures. The tensile CER tests were conducted at 5 testing temperatures between $T=25$ and 90°C by using an Instron type testing machine. The tensile load was applied at both end screws of the FRP joint. The loading-rates (cross-head speeds) were 0.01, 1 and 100mm/min. The tensile fatigue tests were conducted at 5 testing temperatures between $T=25$ and 70°C at a frequency $f=5\text{Hz}$, and 10, 50°C at $f=0.05\text{Hz}$, by using an electro-hydraulic servo testing machine. Load ratio R (minimum load/maximum load) was 0.05. Additionally, the fatigue tests were also conducted at $T=25, 40, 70^{\circ}\text{C}$, $f=5\text{Hz}$ and $R= 0.5, 0.95$.

RESULTS AND DISCUSSION

The CER and fatigue failure of FRP joint occurred in the adhesive resin nearby the interface between cast iron rod and adhesive resin. All failed specimens are similar regardless of loading pattern. We consider, therefore, that the failure mechanisms are the same for CER and fatigue loadings.

Load-elongation Curves

Typical load-elongation curves of FRP joint at various temperatures for CER test are shown in Fig.3. These curves show nonlinear behavior caused by the plastic deformation of adhesive resin. The failure points are defined by the maximum load points on the load-elongation curves.

Fig.2: Configuration of FRP joint.

Fig.3: Load-elongation curves at various Temperature.

Master Curve of CER Failure Load

The left side of Fig.4 shows the CER failure load P_s versus time to failure t_s at various temperatures for FRP joint, where the t_s is defined as the time period from initial loading to P_s in constant elongation-rate test. The master curves of P_s versus reduced failure time t_s' at a reference temperature $T_0 = 40^\circ\text{C}$ as shown in the right side of Fig.4 were constructed by shifting P_s at various temperatures along the log scale of t_s until they overlapped each other. Since P_s at various temperatures can be superimposed smoothly, the time-temperature superposition principle is applicable for P_s .

Fig.4: Master curves of CER failure load P_s .

Figure 5 shows the time-temperature shift factors $a_{T_0}(T)$ for the master curves of P_s for FRP joint. The $a_{T_0}(T)$ are quantitatively in good agreement with Arrhenius' equation by using two different activation energies.

Fig.5: Time-temperature shift factors for P_s .

$$\log a_{T_0}(T) = \frac{\Delta H}{2.303G} \left(\frac{1}{T} - \frac{1}{T_0} \right) \quad (1)$$

Where, ΔH is activation energy [kJ/mol], G is gas constant 8.314×10^{-3} [kJ/(Kmol)].

The dotted lines in this figure show $a_{T_0}(T)$ obtained experimentally for the creep compliance of the adhesive resin. The $a_{T_0}(T)$ for P_s of FRP joint are different from that for D_c of adhesive resin.

Master Curve of Creep Failure Load

We proposed a prediction method of creep failure load P_c from the master curve of CER failure load using the linear cumulative damage law. Let $t_s(P)$ and $t_c(P)$ be the CER and creep failure times for the load P . Suppose that the material experiences a monotone load history $P(t)$ for $0 \leq t \leq t^*$ where t^* is the failure time under this load history. The linear cumulative damage law states

$$\int_0^{t^*} \frac{dt}{t_c[P(t)]} = 1 \quad (2)$$

When $P(t)$ is equal to constant load P_0 , the above formula implies $t^* = t_c(P_0)$.

It is clear from the load-elongation curves shown in Fig.3 that the CER tests employed is approximately equal to constant load tests, that is, creep tests. Therefore, it is not necessary to apply the linear cumulative damage law to the results of CER failure load for predicting the creep failure load. It can be presumed that the CER failure load agrees with the creep failure load.

Fig.6: Master curve for creep failure load.

Figure 6 displays the creep failure load P_c versus time to failure t_c , where P_c is the fatigue failure load at load ratio $R=0.95$. The left side shows the experimental data, while right side exhibits the data shifted to $T_0=40^\circ\text{C}$ using the shift factors for CER failure load. Since P_c at

various temperatures can be superimposed smoothly, the time-temperature superposition principle is also applicable for P_c .

The right side of this figure also displays the master curve for the CER failure load in the curve of thick line. The experimental P_c does not agree with the predicted P_c but agrees well with CER failure load P_s , because the loading pattern for CER test is similar to that for creep test as shown In Fig.3.

Master Curve of Fatigue Failure Load

We regard the fatigue failure load P_f either as a function of the number of cycles to failure N_f or of the time to failure $t_f=N_f/f$ for a combination of f , R , T and denote them by $P_f(N_f; f, R, T)$ or $P_f(t_f; f, R, T)$. Further, we consider that the CER failure load $P_s(t_f; T)$ is equal to the fatigue failure load at $N_f=1/2$ and $R=0$ by choosing $t_f=1/(2f)$. At this point, we introduce special symbols for fatigue failure load at zero and unit load ratios by $P_{f,0}$ and $P_{f,1}$ where the latter corresponds to creep failure load.

To describe the master curve of $P_{f,0}$, we need the reduced frequency f' in addition to the reduced time t_f' , each defined by

$$f' = f \cdot a_{T_0}(T) \quad t_f' = \frac{t_f}{a_{T_0}(T)} = \frac{N_f}{f'} \quad (3)$$

Thus, the master curve has the form, $P_{f,0}(t_f'; f', T_0)$. An alternative form of the master curve is possible by suppressing the explicit dependence on frequency in favor of N_f as $P_{f,0}(t_f'; N_f, T_0)$. Recall that the master curve of fatigue failure load at $N_f= 1/2$ reduces to the master curve of CER failure load.

Fig.7: P_f - N_f curves at $f=5\text{Hz}$.

The fatigue failure load P_f versus the number of cycles to failure N_f (P_f - N_f curve) for FRP joint at frequency $f=5\text{Hz}$ and load ratio $R=0.05$ are shown in Fig.7. The P_f depends remarkably on temperature as well as N_f .

Fig.8: Master curves of fatigue failure load.

The upper portion of Fig.8 shows P_f versus the reduced time to failure t_f' . On the other hand, each point on the master curves of constant reduced frequency represents a number of cycles to failure. Connecting the points of the same N_f with these curves, the master curves of P_f for constant N_f are constructed as shown in the lower side of Fig.8. From this figure, it is found that the fatigue failure load depends scarcely on the number of cycles to failure.

Fig.9: P_f - N_f curves at $f=0.05$ Hz.

The P_f - N_f curves of FRP joint at $f=0.05$ Hz and $R=0.05$ are shown in Fig.9. The solid lines in this figure indicate the predicted P_f - N_f curves at $T=10$ and 50°C obtained from the master curves of fatigue failure load as shown in the lower side of Fig.8. The predicted P_f - N_f curves

agree with the experimental data. Therefore, the time-temperature superposition principle for CER failure load also holds for the fatigue failure load, and the hypothesis (B) is valid for fatigue failure load.

Fatigue Failure Load for Arbitrary Load Ratio

We have the master curve for creep failure load $P_c(t_c'; T_0)$ from which follows the creep failure load at any temperature T . The creep failure load, in turn, may be regarded the fatigue failure load $P_{f,1}(t_f; f, T)$ at unit load ratio $R=1$ and arbitrary frequency f with $t_c = t_f$. Further, from the master curve for fatigue failure load at zero load ratio, we can deduce the fatigue failure load $P_{f,0}(t_f; f, T)$ at zero load ratio for any frequency f and temperature T .

Invoking the hypothesis (D), we propose a formula to estimate the fatigue failure load $P_f(t_f; f, R, T)$ at an arbitrary combination of f, R, T by:

$$P_f(t_f; f, R, T) = P_{f,1}(t_f; f, T)R + P_{f,0}(t_f; f, T)(1 - R) \quad (4)$$

Figure 10 shows experimental data of P_f - N_f for $f=5\text{Hz}$, $R=0.5$ and $T=25, 40,$ and 70°C . The curves of $R=0.05$ and 0.95 respectively represent the least squares fit for experimental data of fatigue test of $R=0.05$ and 0.95 . The curve of $R=0.5$ is calculated from equation (4) on the basis of the curves for $R=0.05$ and $R=0.95$. As can be seen, the predictions correspond well with the experimental data. Therefore, the hypothesis (D) is valid for fatigue failure load. From this figure, it is found that the fatigue failure load depends scarcely on load ratio at all temperature tested.

Fig.10: P_f - N_f curves at $R=0.5$.

Comparison of the Master Curves of Fatigue Failure Load for Two Kinds of FRP Joints

Figure 11 shows the master curves of fatigue failure load for FRP joints comparing with those for FRP joints in which a brittle epoxy resin, Mavidon^{AE}, is used for adhesives [9]. It is found from this figure that the fatigue failure load for FRP joints using a brittle epoxy adhesive decreases remarkably with the number of cycles to failure as well as time to failure and temperature. On the other hand, fatigue failure load for FRP joints using a ductile PMMA adhesive decreases remarkably with time to failure and temperature, however decreases scarcely with the number of cycles to failure.

Fig.11: Comparison of the master curves of fatigue failure load.

CONCLUSION

We proposed a prediction method of fatigue life for polymer composites and structures under an arbitrary frequency, stress ratio (minimum stress/maximum stress), and temperature from the results of constant strain-rate (CSR) and fatigue tests under various temperatures and loading rates. Tensile tests of GFRP/metal adhesive joints for CSR and fatigue loadings were conducted for various temperatures and loading rates. The validity of this method was proven for the tensile fatigue life for the GFRP/metal adhesive joints from these test results. Furthermore, the characteristic time-temperature dependent fatigue behavior of this FRP joints was clarified using this prediction method.

REFERENCES

1. Aboudi, J. and G. Cederbaum, Composite Structures, 12 (1989), p.243.
2. Ha, S.K. and G. S. Springer, J. Composite Materials, 23 (1989), p.1159.
3. Sullivan, J.L., Composite Science and Technology, 39 (1990), p.207.
4. Miyano, Y., M. Kanemitsu, T. Kunio, and H. Kuhn, J. Composite Materials, 20 (1986), p.520.

5. Miyano, Y., M. K. McMurray, J. Enyama, and M. Nakada, *J. Composite Materials*, 28 (1994), p.1250.
6. Miyano, Y., M. K. McMurray, N. Kitade, M. Nakada, and M. Mohri, *Advanced Composite Materials*, 4 (1994), p.87.
7. Miyano, Y., M. Nakada, and M. K. McMurray, *J. Composite Materials*, 29 (1995), p.1808.
8. Miyano, Y., M. Nakada, and R. Muki, *Mechanics of Time-Dependent Materials*, 1 (1997), p.143.
9. Miyano, Y., S. W. Tsai, M. Nakada, S. Sihn, and T. Imai, *Proc. ICCM/11*, (1997), VI, p.26.
10. Miyano, Y., M. Nakada, M. K. McMurray, and R. Muki, *J. Composite Materials*, 31 (1997), p.619.
11. Nakada, M., T. Ishiguro, and Y. Miyano, *Proc. ICCM/11*, (1997), II, p.167.